

REPORT:

A3.4.9: Light Duty to Heavy Duty Gap Analysis Results

Authors: Jamie Malkinson, Ashley Brown, Thor Anders Aarhaug, Ole Kjos,
Christian Spitta, Matz Dietrich, Etienne Basset, Ward Storms, Thomas
Bacquart

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Author(s) Jamie Malkinson ITM Power Ashley Brown ITM Power Thor Anders Aarhaug SINTEF Ole Kjos SINTEF Christian Spitta ZBT Matz Dietrich ZBT Etienne Basset ENGIE Ward Storms TME Thomas Bacquart NPL	Pages 17 pages
<p>Summary</p> <p>The implementation of hydrogen fuel sampling at heavy-duty hydrogen refuelling stations (HD-HRS) is critical to ensure that trucks and bus fleet would operate within expected performance and lifetime. The report proposed a gap analysis light duty to heavy duty sampling investigating safety aspect (i.e., flow, venting and pressure relief system), engineering and mechanical aspect (i.e., connection to nozzle, filling rate) and metrological aspects (i.e., sample representativeness). The gap analysis table provided an initial guidance to address the transition to heavy duty HRS sampling for hydrogen fuel.</p> <p>This report was written as part of activity 3.4.9 from the EMPIR Metrology for Hydrogen Vehicles 2 (MetroHyVe2) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st August 2020 and focused on providing solutions to four measurement challenges faced by the hydrogen industry (flow metering, quality assurance, quality control, sampling and fuel cell stack testing). For more details about this project please visit https://www.sintef.no/projectweb/metrohyve-2/.</p>	
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Introduction

The implementation of hydrogen fuel sampling at heavy-duty hydrogen refuelling stations (HD-HRS) is critical to ensure that trucks and bus fleet would operate within expected performance and lifetime. The hydrogen fuel sampling at HD-HRS with complexity in term of implementation and safety.

The MetroHyVe 2 partners had reviewed the different sampling systems (HyDAC, Qualitizer, Hy-SAM, Air Liquide sampler, ENGIE spot sampling system, sampling system compliant to ASTM D7606) evaluating the challenges to perform sampling of hydrogen fuel at HD-HRS. The gap analysis was not designed to provide guidance on the requirements of a specific sampling system. Therefore, the activities investigate the different sampling strategy defined as parallel sampling, direct /serial sampling and particulate sampling independently. The definition of HD-HRS was filling of hydrogen at maximum flow rate of 120 g/s and minimum temperature of -40 degree Celsius.

The gap analysis investigates safety aspect such as flow, venting and pressure relief system, engineering and mechanical aspect such as connection to nozzle, filling rate of the cylinder and metrological aspects such as sample representativeness. The gap analysis table was considering most of the points above as an initial guidance to address the transition to heavy duty HRS sampling for hydrogen fuel.

GAP analysis table

Table 1. MetroHyVe 2 Light Duty to Heavy Duty Gap Analysis Results. The acronyms used are HD - Heavy Duty; LD - Light Duty and HRS - Hydrogen Refuelling Station. The sampling method are classified into parallel sampling, serial / direct sampling and particulate sampling.

MetroHyVe 2 Light Duty to Heavy Duty Gap Analysis Results				
Sampling method	Challenge	Gap to Heavy Duty	Further detail	Challenges / ideas
Parallel Sampling	Receptacle / Nozzle	HD and LD nozzles and Receptacles are of different design and not cross compatible.	New Receptacle and nozzle required for sampling system. Availability of HD -40°C and 120g/s nozzles is a challenge.	How to include universal receptacle or exchangeable receptacle in sampling system design? Engineering/mechanical verification
	Filling of cylinder	Flow on HD is 120g/s vs 60g/s on LD. Therefore, the sample cylinder will fill more quickly.	The flow to the sample cylinder needs to be adjusted to slow down the fill. On HySam a needle valve can be adjusted, however on systems that use an orifice this will have to be changed (e.g., Qualitizer).	How to adjust cylinder filling rates on sampling system design? Impact of the cylinder filling rate on the actual sample obtained? Engineering/mechanical verification + metrology / quality study
	Compliance	Flow on HD is 120g/s vs 60g/s on LD therefore physical changes are required to sample system to account for increased flow rate.	Sample systems will require re-certification, which may be complicated without manufacturer engagement.	How to ensure that retrofitted system is compliant? Engineering/mechanical verification + documentation
	Buffer tank	If a buffer tank is used instead of a vehicle, a larger buffer tank than the current 60l will be required.	Large buffer tanks present logistical problems and are more difficult to vent safely on site.	To avoid the use of FCEV, there is a clear safety (venting) and logistic challenges in the use of buffer/mock-up tank in coherence with heavy duty refuelling

Parallel Sampling	Filling protocol	There is a requirement to add a communications protocol between sampling system and refueller in future.	Communications protocol will have to be tailored to HD sample system. It may be possible to use this to mitigate need for a large vessel.	
	Intermediate pipework	Flow on HD is 120g/s vs 60g/s on LD, therefore tubing and fittings between nozzle and Receptacle may cause a flow restriction.	Diameter of pipework and fittings will require evaluation, and may require modification to maintain normal refuelling flow and pressure.	How to ensure that retrofitted system is compliant? Engineering/mechanical verification
	Vent design	Flow on HD is 120g/s vs 60g/s on LD, therefore current vent assembly may restrict flow.	Diameter of pipework and fittings will require evaluation, and may require modification to remove restrictions	How to ensure that retrofitted system is compliant? Engineering/mechanical verification
	Pressure relief valve	Pressure on HD sampling is 350barg vs 700barg on LD.	Unlikely to need to change pressure relief valve as operating pressure of sample system has not been increased.	No change needed
Serial / Direct Sampling	Receptacle	HD and LD nozzles are of different design requiring different receptacles.	Receptacle will need replacement/modification, however there is a receptacle available that is compatible with both LD and HD.	How to include universal receptacle or exchangeable receptacle in sampling system design?
	Representativeness of sample	Similar to LD, is the direct sample representative of the hydrogen fuel delivered to a vehicle.	HRS is in maintenance mode and direct sampling is short. This may be less representative for higher flow rates of HD.	How to ensure representative sample is obtained? Metrological verification
	Sampling Conditions	Pressure, flow, venting and purging volumes will be different between HD and LD.	Conditions need to be defined before taking samples. Appropriate preparations need to be made as large venting volumes, or multiple samples may be required.	How to ensure representative sample is obtained? Metrological verification + safety requirement
	Filling protocol	As HRS is operating in maintenance mode, the communication protocol is not required.	Sampling parameters may need adjustment between LD and HD.	How to ensure representative sample is obtained? Metrological verification + safety requirement
Particulate Sampling	Receptacle / Nozzle	HD and LD nozzles and Receptacles are of different design and not cross compatible.	New Receptacle and nozzle required for sampling system. Availability of HD -40C and 120g/s nozzles is a challenge.	
	Pressure drop across filter	Flow on HD is 120g/s vs 60g/s on LD. Therefore, there will be a higher pressure drop across the particulate filter.	Risk of damage to filter. Filling event may abort due to high pressure drop.	
	Filter behaviour at high flow rate	Flow on HD is 120g/s vs 60g/s on LD, which may have an effect on filter behaviour.	High flow rate may damage filter resulting in mass loss, therefore particulate mass is underestimated during measurement.	